

Accepted Manuscript

“Dynamic traffic noise assessment tool: a comparative study between a roundabout and a signalised intersection”

Laura Estévez-Mauriz, Jens Forssén

PII: S0003-682X(17)30118-4

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2017.09.003>

Reference: APAC 6256

To appear in: *Applied Acoustics*

Received Date: 1 February 2017

Revised Date: 28 August 2017

Accepted Date: 5 September 2017

Please cite this article as: Estévez-Mauriz, L., Forssén, J., “Dynamic traffic noise assessment tool: a comparative study between a roundabout and a signalised intersection”, *Applied Acoustics* (2017), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2017.09.003>

This is a PDF file of an unedited manuscript that has been accepted for publication. As a service to our customers we are providing this early version of the manuscript. The manuscript will undergo copyediting, typesetting, and review of the resulting proof before it is published in its final form. Please note that during the production process errors may be discovered which could affect the content, and all legal disclaimers that apply to the journal pertain.

“Dynamic traffic noise assessment tool: a comparative study between a roundabout and a signalised intersection”

Laura Estévez-Mauriz^{a,*}, Jens Forssén^a

^a*Division of Applied Acoustics, Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, SE-412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden*

Abstract

Considering traffic flow as a steady noise source is common practice when studying traffic alternatives and its impact on the sound environment. However, vehicle dynamics have a strong influence on both transport behaviour and noise emission. One of the most relevant elements of traffic design is the intersection, where replacement of crossing intersections with roundabouts is common. In order to understand the features of these two traffic configurations, microscopic approaches are needed, making it possible to study time-pattern fluctuations relevant for the urban sound environment perception. A model based on individual-vehicle characteristics as function of time is developed and implemented in a real case study at a development stage. The model incorporates state-of-art microscopic traffic simulation software combined with the recent noise emission model, CNOSSOS-EU, applied through an in-house developed dynamic traffic noise tool, including both internal combustion engine and all-electric vehicles at different traffic flows. The tool is described in general terms incorporating the randomisation of source power. The propagation considers a flat-city configuration up to 100 m range. The tool enables study of different statistical indicators, including descriptors of probability density functions, calm periods through the novel indicator Centre of Mass Time (CMT) and

*Corresponding author

Email address: `laura.estevez@chalmers.se` (Laura Estévez-Mauriz)

noise events. The outcomes are presented through graphs and maps explaining traffic disruptions, acceleration effects, vehicle configurations and flows, source strengths, contribution and difference maps. Among the results, it is shown that, for the signalised crossing, the acceleration of the simulated traffic has a large effect on the source strength. It is however also shown that, for an unbalanced roundabout intersection leading to congestions, it can become noisier than the signalised crossing. It is furthermore shown that, when reducing the traffic flow, the two intersection types behave more similarly; however the roundabout having the best performance for the majority of the studied analysis. Further results are shown, e.g. for removing heavy vehicles, removing also medium heavy vehicles and assuming only all-electric light vehicles, including analysis from using various indicators. A discussion about the presented tool, the current results and ideas for future work concludes the paper.

The present paper goes along a series of studies with the overall intention to provide a more solid basis for justifying decisions in traffic planning regarding the outdoor sound environment.

Keywords: road traffic noise, urban sound environment, traffic dynamics, prediction, modeling

1. Introduction

Being able to control the acoustic environment is a fundamental question in order to support liveable cities, especially at the current densification processes. The available means of transport and the spatial pattern characteristics are largely dictating the urban form. A careful planning is the key to avoid poor patches in the urban configuration and future economical burden.

Transport is not only the major noise source in cities [1]. It has been strongly linked to noise annoyance, sleep disturbance and numerous health effects [2]. Latest data on noise exposure in Europe [3] suggested that 42 million of European citizens are exposed to road traffic noise levels above the targets of the World Health Organisation ($L_{den}=55$ dB). This high exposure is partly caused

by the urban and traffic planning, as well as by the building design.

One of the common attempts to control the sound environment is to adopt Action Plans based upon strategic noise-mapping results according to the Environmental Noise Directive (END) [4]. Although several investigations have identified measures to reduce traffic noise [5–7], the traffic flow is normally considered as non-dynamic. This assumption is used as well to build the strategic noise maps using commercial noise mapping software. The resulting time-averaged A-weighted sound pressure levels and its derivations as L_{den} , L_n , L_d are the output of these maps intended to study large areas, e.g. a city.

For high traffic variations, as the ones present in (dense) urban environments, this analysis leads to miss-estimations [8–10]. Moreover, annoyance and certain aspects of sleep disturbance have been related to the identification of noise events resulting from variations in traffic flow [11, 12]. The influence of noise events remains as an open question, pointing out the existence of a threshold and their effect on annoyance [13, 14], or the inability of humans to distinguish between situations as vehicle flow increases and the noise is perceived as a continuum[15], suggesting that further studies need to be made to understand the detection mechanism of events. In this context, the study of traffic transformations requires a microscopic approach that includes traffic behaviour and vehicle kinematics, opening the study to the time-pattern fluctuations through the instantaneous sound pressure levels relevant to describe the urban sound environment and study the suitability of human activities [8, 16].

Intersections have been considered as the main factor to assess the performance of the road network. In order to improve the traffic design, a common practice in recent decades has been the replacement of crossing intersections with roundabouts. This transformation, apart from political decisions, is based mainly on the increased safety for pedestrians [17], and has been argued as well to plausibly reduce the noise. The main difference among these intersection designs is based on the drivers' capacity to accept or deny gaps in the roundabout compared with the signalised crossing characterised by a stop-controlled situation. In the first one, the workload is mainly on the driver [18].

Vehicle kinematics have been pointed out as a characteristic with strong influence on the vehicles' noise emission and hence, on the sound environment [9, 16, 19–22]. As a consequence, several models have been developed. In order to mention some of the most relevant ones, three models are highlighted here. The model developed by EPFL called DRONE [23] uses AVENUE as traffic simulation model and the ASJ Model-1998 for the noise estimation. The lanes are divided into segments and the vehicles are located at the centre of each segment. The effect of buildings is included based on a statistical approach. The model developed by Ghent University [19] uses PARAMICS as micro-simulation model, where the noise emission values are only function of speed and vehicle type. Here, a beamtrace 2.5D propagation model is included, counting for multiple reflections. PARAMICS uses a space-discrete system, opposed to VISSIM, which is space-continuous. The acoustic model is based on the Nord2000 vehicle noise emission database. When the simulation is too large, the exact positions of vehicles is not accounted for and a grid is used instead. The third model mentioned is the one developed by INRETS/CSTB [24], using SYMUVIA as a component of the noise simulation package SYMUBRUIT, fed in studies as in [9] with the noise emission laws from the FHWA database, where the emission depends on the speed and the throttle states specified by two acceleration rates: full or cruising throttle. Other studies using SYMUVIA, such as the validation in [25], rely on NMPB-Routes-96 noise emission model, accounting as well for geometric sound attenuation. Another emission law followed is the one based on the outcomes of a previous work [26], using the propagation model NMPB-Routes-96 implemented in the Mithra software [16]. The SYMUVIA traffic modelling has been improved to account for several traffic conditions including e.g. lane-changing phenomena [21]. For example, different scenarios were tested where one of them replaces a traffic signal by a roundabout [16]. In those scenarios, the noise emission is estimated through noise cells defined by their sound power level, with sizes of 10 m between road sections and 5 m at intersections, and only the vehicles present in the cell contribute. Moreover, the model used assumes that all vehicles are equal in terms of sound power.

The model presented in the present paper does not rely on this assumption.
75 The CNOSSOS-EU model [27], where the noise emission of a certain vehicle
at a certain time-step depends on the current speed and acceleration, together
with the vehicle type. In this sense, within the same vehicle type and same
values of acceleration and speed, the noise emission will be the same. Once
this is computed, a variability in the emission among the same vehicle type is
80 inserted. This variability has been proven relevant in the assessment of peaks of
noise estimation [28], and included within dynamic traffic noise models [28–45].
The variation in emissions are further explained in section 2.1. Randomisation
of source power.

The breakpoint of these models, including the present one, is the introduction of
85 indicators to reflect urban traffic noise dynamics. Classical descriptors based on
long-term measurements have been proven inefficient to reflect not only short-
term, but as well long-term variations [20], being unable to describe the sound
variations in the built environment. Specific indicators have been used to reflect
traffic evolution over time. For example, noise fluctuations indicators have been
90 proposed to distinguish between traffic cycles and the percentage of these when
the maximum sound pressure level exceeds a certain value [20]. The indica-
tors have also been influenced by those of room acoustics, e.g. the noise rating
curves, suggested to highlight emergent frequencies [29]. Other indicators try to
relate pleasantness in a musical context with the road traffic noise rhythm [19].
95 As previously mentioned, sound events have been highlighted as an opportunity
to study nuisance [30], and indicators underlying noisy periods have been stud-
ied, either relative to a statistical value or to a fixed noise level value [31, 32].
The present paper introduces indicators regarding noise events and calm peri-
ods, e.g. the novel indicator called Centre of Mass Time (CMT) attempting to
100 study the weight of quiet periods clustering as explained in section 2.2. Noise
descriptors.

The methodology of study results in a time-pattern analysis tool capable to il-
lustrate and explain the influence of the traffic dynamics and the effect of noise
emission of each vehicle. The output power level is then computed each 0.1 s

105 for all vehicle positions present during the calculation hour. The propagation
modelling includes pressure doubling due to hard ground conditions and sound
attenuation due to geometric spreading under a flat city configuration. This
way, the modelling tool is used to make an initial study of a large variety of sta-
tistical indicators, including descriptors of probability density functions, calm
110 periods and noise events, as well as visual outcomes such as contribution and
difference maps.

The tool is tested on a real case scenario under development in the city of
Gothenburg, with a high traffic stream. In the comparison of the two types of
intersections, the traffic demands are the same, requiring adaptations in terms
115 of road configurations, among other characteristics explained in the paper. The
advantages of the model are that it uses state-of-art traffic simulation tool and
incorporates a variation in the sound power level to adapt it to more realistic
situations. Novel indicators to reflect the cluster and weighting of quiet periods
are incorporated. The tool is tested with realistic complex cases holding the
120 same demands regarding the origin-destination matrices, requiring adaptations
in the traffic layout.

2. Dynamic traffic noise tool

The purpose of the tool is to study the resulting sound environment through
the analysis of road traffic noise emission computed from single vehicles as func-
125 tion of time. The focus is on studying small areas, where a simplified model can
describe the main characteristics. The tool consists of two main parts, the micro-
scopic traffic simulation and the noise emission models. The first part involves
the utilisation of a microscopic traffic software, capable to give dynamic outputs
in the form of position, speed and acceleration versus time. For the purpose of
130 this paper, the software used was the car-following model VISSIM v6. VISSIM is
a microscopic, behaviour and time-based simulation where driver-vehicle-units
are modelled as single objects. It is a path-based simulator, meaning that it
incorporates path-based routings instead of the one used in PARAMICS, which

is link-based. Also, it includes driver behaviour enhancements, where the driver
135 model is a psycho-physic one (closer to real decisions taken in traffic) developed by Wiedemann, incorporating the Wiedemann 74 model for urban traffic situations [33]. The network is defined by links and connectors, having different properties describing its characteristics, e.g. coordinates, lane number and width, banned overtaking by heavy vehicles. The traffic flow is not uniformly
140 distributed, and the number of departures responds to a Poisson distribution. Traffic control for the non-signalised intersections respond to the right-of-way (right-hand traffic) as a priority rule. Signalised intersections are controlled by signal groups gathering multiple signal heads. According to Wiedemann 74 driving behaviour, the minimum headway is set to 0.50 m and average stand-
145 still distance is 2 m. As a stochastic distribution is present, acceleration and deceleration values are the result of functions of maximum and desired acceleration and deceleration. The acceleration curves included in the software respond to western European data, and no further refinement was specified by the corresponding road authorities, however, the incorporation of finer adapted data
150 would largely improve results reliability. Further details about the traffic simulation tool can be found at [34]. Within this model, assumptions, adaptations and calibrations need to be performed, based on a stipulated Origin-Destination (OD) matrix, as well as speed and acceleration profile data (circulatory and approaching lanes), road configuration, traffic signal cycle length, individual traffic
155 behaviour, vehicle composition, and other modelled specifications following the considerations for intersections of [35–38]. The input data may respond to a current or a future scenario, in which data gathering from similar situations is needed. In order to allow a sufficient amount of vehicle data captures in the sense of vehicle records, a resolution for all calculations in the present paper
160 of 10 time steps per simulation second is performed, with a duration of 3600 s divided in four quarters. In order to stabilise the traffic, a warm-up time of 300 s are added at the beginning of the simulation, and 300 s are added at the end to complete all trips.

The second part of the tool constitutes the main development. It takes the

165 results from the microscopic traffic simulation over time as an input, and computes the source strength as function of time for each individual vehicle present during the simulation record (see Fig. 1). Recently, the END introduced a common methodological framework to be used in strategic noise mapping. The road traffic noise source emission proposed included in the "Common Noise Assessment Methods", known as CNOSSOS-EU, is implemented [27], including two main noise generators or components: rolling and propulsion noise. Both are represented as a single output point source located at the centre of the vehicle at 0.05 m above the road surface. The method incorporates three vehicle categories grouped into light, medium-heavy and heavy vehicles. So far, it is developed for a frequency range between 63 Hz and 8 kHz in octave bands. Further study including two-wheeler vehicles is of interest, however at the current state, few data regarding the traffic configuration parameters is available.

Figure 1: Scheme of the dynamic traffic noise tool.

Within the CNOSSOS-EU method, the noise that is produced by the vehicles is described according to parameters of speed and vehicle category. Moreover, corrections are performed due to environmental effects and the effect of acceleration and deceleration cycles. To calculate the sound power level emitted

as function of vehicle speed, a speed limitation between 20 and 130 km/h is set. In this paper, the model was used beyond its limitations in terms of minimum speed. The effect of the low speed becomes more relevant in case the
185 propulsion noise is suppressed and only the rolling noise, with a logarithmic dependence, is contributing e.g. for electric vehicles. To consider a scenario composed by electric vehicles, the model used suggested correction terms applied to the propulsion noise component [39, 40]. The corrections included the frequency range between 63 Hz and 4 kHz, whereby they were extrapolated to
190 8 kHz to fit the CNOSSOS-EU method.

Since the microscopic traffic simulation is giving as output the exact values of acceleration or deceleration of each vehicle, the CNOSSOS-EU acceleration calculation was replaced by the more advanced acceleration and deceleration effect according to the Harmonoise engineering model [41]. The Harmonoise
195 correction is limited to a range between 2 m/s^2 and -2 m/s^2 . All vehicles with higher or lower acceleration values were set to 2 m/s^2 or -2 m/s^2 respectively. However, in this method, the effect of breaking is only included in the propulsion noise. For the purpose of the type of study, the tool includes pressure doubling due to hard ground conditions and sound attenuation due to
200 geometric spreading in a flat city configuration, meaning that the model does not include diffraction/reflection around buildings.

The developed model is validated through a comparison with analytical modelling. For this purpose, the effect of acceleration was removed from the calculation in the developed model and a simplified study case was chosen, with
205 a single lane of 400 m length. The traffic flow was set to 140 veh/h including only light vehicles with a speed limit of 50 km/h and a lane-width of 3.25 m. The analytical modelling is based on the CNOSSOS-EU source model and non-refractive propagation above hard ground. The differences on the equivalent sound pressure level regarding the analytical modelling and the developed
210 tool were 2.5 dBA at 400 m, 1.4 dBA at 200 m, 0.9 dBA at 100 m, 0.6 dBA at 50 m, and 0.2 dBA at 10 m. The differences between them increased with distance, responding to the effect of air attenuation. Since the model lacks of

air attenuation, the results showed that at the current status, it is reliable up to a distance of 100 m from the source, accepting an error of 1 dB at most.

215 *2.1. Randomisation of source power*

The CNOSSOS-EU road traffic source modelling presents a sound power level function, where vehicles driving at a certain speed always have the same source strength, making it difficult to model the variability of measured data. On the other hand, the old Nordic Method [42] approach describes a randomness of the power level following a Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation that decays exponentially with driving speed. The approach is used here, however, the values of the standard deviations are updated according to [43], for light and heavy vehicles as described in [44]. (The medium heavy vehicles are here given the same standard deviation as the heavy vehicles.) Each individual vehicle is assigned a random number later scaled according to vehicle type and driving speed. It should also be noted that the total power level is adjusted such that the expected energetic mean coincides with the CNOSSOS-EU model. The resulting standard deviations are plotted in Fig. 2. The motivation for choosing this approach lies in its balance between simplicity and possibility to model the main features of the variability. Newer data records exist in literature [45, 46], however, their amount and scope is currently deemed insufficient as basis for a new model.

Figure 2: Resulting standard deviations used in the randomisation of source power.

Results in Fig. 3 show that the inclusion of randomisation gives a more realistic scenario, illustrated by the effect of randomisation as function of time and the corresponding histograms. For the not-randomised situations, the sound power levels have both a lower limit and a strong peak corresponding to zero

acceleration, resulting in an unnatural situation. This is shown as well in the sound power level distribution, where an unnatural large part of the records in the non-randomised cases has a sound power level of 84 dBA, corresponding to still-standing vehicles.

Figure 3: Example of randomisation influence on sound power level at crossing (left) and roundabout (right).

2.2. Noise descriptors

The microscopic traffic modelling allows the representation of 1-second equivalent sound pressure levels, $L_{Aeq,1s}$, with a traffic evolution over the simulated time (1 h). Time-pattern representations are valuable to assess the soft qualities of the built environment, as the sound environment. It enables the introduction of a set of indicators related to noise events and calm periods, in addition to the ones linked with the histograms of levels, e.g. L_{A90} , L_{A50} , L_{A10} , which denote levels exceeded 90%, 50%, 10% of the time. On this subject, noise peaks and traffic flow characteristics, e.g. clustered or even, have been suggested to help in the study of noise annoyance [47]. It has been proven that sleep disturbance, annoyance and human activity interference are related to events in the noise signal, where the number of events, the duration and the level become relevant [11, 13, 15, 48, 49]. In a way to consider the exposure time pattern, two indicators are included, one related to noise events and a novel indicator related to calm periods and its clustering.

Number of events (NE): for the purpose of these study and based on the studies gathered in [30], an event is qualified as such that the chosen noise level/indicator threshold is exceeded, lasting for at least 3 seconds and finished

when the level has decreased 3 dBA from the threshold. It is stated as a func-
 260 tion of a certain indicator, e.g. L_{A50} , or of a noise level interval (e.g. $60 < L_{eq}$
 < 65 dBA, as the equivalent noise level between 60 and 65 dBA).

Centre of Mass Time (CMT): in order to have a better understanding of the
 opportunities to recover from high noise levels through larger periods of reduced
 noise, the intention is to measure clustering of quiet periods, as its distribution
 265 may be linked with the impact on activity interference. The concept of CMT,
 measured in seconds, experiments with the weighting of such clustering. At pe-
 riods of time when the noise level is lower than the one indicated as the limiting
 one (e.g. L_{A50}), a weight is given to the period, increasing linearly with the
 period time length. The indicator premiates few larger values of quiet periods
 270 rather to many small ones. For example, quiet periods of two different situa-
 tions are recorded under a variable named a representing the vector of less noisy
 periods. In the first case, $a=[10]$ as one unique quiet period of 10-second; in
 the second case, $a = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1]$, where 10 periods of 1-second are
 recorded. CMT is given by:

$$CMT = \frac{\sum(a^2)}{\sum(a)} \quad (1)$$

275 As a result, a single 10-second "quiet period" is given a ten times higher value
 than ten 1-second "quiet periods", penalising the fragmentation of quieter pe-
 riods and valuing its clustering.

3. Case study on traffic strategies

280 With the purpose of analysing a realistic and complex case that can be of
 interest for the traffic authorities, a road intersection proposed by the city is
 used as the case study. The intersection belongs to the new urban development
 known as "Frihamnen area" in the city of Gothenburg, Sweden. The utilisa-
 tion of a real case scenario gives the opportunity to not only illustrate scenarios
 closer to the current urban development, but also to use more realistic data.

285 The Frihamnen area will allocate around 15,000 inhabitants and the same num-

ber of working places in an area of 1 km² [50]. Due to its location and scope, the plan is considered by the government as one of the key projects and a test-bed within the numerous urban developments in the city. The inclusion of roundabout or crossing intersection types is seen as an open question, since a large amount of traffic is planned to cross through this area every day. This has consequences in the transportation system and mobility, but moreover, in the quality of the surrounding spaces including environmental consequences in both air and noise pollution.

A preliminary traffic planning, indicating vehicle streams and preliminary layout configuration, has been realised by "Trafik-kontoret" (TK), the Traffic Office of Gothenburg, used as a basis for analysis. The peak hour traffic flow was calculated following the recommendations in [51], simulating the worst scenario within a year. The average desired speed was set to 53 km/h; for the approaching lanes, it was set to 30 km/h and the average circulatory speed set to 17 km/h. The traffic flow is indicated in Fig. 5. Also, a reduction of 25% was studied to compare two traffic stream scenarios. Simulations were carried for an hour, having a buffer of 5 min at the beginning and 5 min at the end, allowing all vehicles to reach their destination. To allow a real comparison, the OD matrix is the same for both intersection types, whereby the same number of vehicles have to follow a route and reach their destination. This required a series of adaptations in the road configuration regarding the capacity needs, including the addition of a second lane and turning lanes. In order to study the effect of vehicle type, three different ones were studied (see Table 1) varying according to the current situation in the area in terms of vehicle distribution. The vehicles types included corresponded to light vehicles (LV), medium-heavy vehicles (MHV) and heavy vehicles (HV), regarding the CNOSSOS-EU categorisation, which were equated to the vehicles available in the microscopic traffic software. Moreover, scenarios with only LV were also compared with all-electric ones.

Case	% Vehicles		
	1	2	3
1) LV, MHV, HV	92	4	4
2) LV, MHV	96	4	-
3) LV	100	-	-

Table 1: Cases including the vehicle categories and its distribution for the signalised crossing and roundabout intersection.

In order to cope with the same traffic stream, different transportation network requisites need to be modelled. Following the recommendations in [37], the number of vehicles, the flow rate, the number of lanes, as well as the number of through, storage and turning lanes, the cycle length and phases (for the crossing intersection) are modelled accordingly. In both intersection types the lane length was set to 200 m as a representative distance between intersections [19]. Parameters including maximum entry and circulatory speed in the roundabout, lane change of heavy vehicles, stop lines, priority rules for both intersections and conflict markers are also modelled, based on recommendations in [9, 17, 18, 37, 38, 52]. The desired speed set in the model is valid until the geometric characteristics or the traffic conditions compel with the speed to be adjusted. Modelling reduced speed areas in approaching lanes need to be included. To calibrate the intersections according to speed profiles, similar data from Gothenburg city was used in terms of traffic flow and road configuration [53]. Speed profiles were constructed through a probability distribution with 85% of vehicles driving below the signed speed of 50 km/h.

The present study does not intend to address the impact that a macro-scale transport design will have on the micro-scale intersection design. In this case, the tool intends to control and analyse key features in a way that a smaller number of variables are present. This allow us to reduce the study to an area around 500m by 500m, whereas the length of the lanes approaching and leaving the intersection is set to 200m as a representative distance between main intersections in urban environments [54]. This length will let the vehicles flow towards the intersection with the possibility to reach their desired speed. An instant of the microscopic traffic simulation is captured in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Microscopic traffic simulation instant of the signalised crossing (left) and the roundabout intersection (right).

The forecasted traffic of the worst plausible scenario according to the prognosis data (peak hour in the afternoon for the peak month) is indicated in Fig. 5. High variations in traffic stream can be appreciated and adaptations in the layout number of lanes have been reflected in the present road configuration. To perform a comparison among results, 12 points set as plausible receivers were selected (see Fig. 5), with equivalent distances for both intersection types. Four of them (1-4) are located close to the intersection, four more at 100 m from the lanes (5-8), and four at the sidewalk of the east-west lanes (9-12). Even though points located at further distances (5-8) might be shielded by obstacles (buildings), these points were included since the area might contain several open spaces, as parks or squares, directly exposed to road traffic noise.

Figure 5: Traffic flow at both intersections and location of study points.

350 4. Results

To study the differences in the acoustic performance of both intersection types and the two traffic conditions (peak hour and 25% traffic reduction from

peak hour) within the 3 different cases (1. LV, MHV, HV; 2. LV, MHV; 3. LV),
a series of results in the form of plots and maps are presented together with a
355 discussion regarding the findings. Selected scenarios are chosen to reflect differ-
ences in behaviour. These results include traffic characteristics, speed evolution
over time, effect of acceleration in the source strength, sound pressure level dif-
ferences, contribution maps and time patterns, as well as statistical descriptors
to explain calm periods, time ratios, and events.

360 4.1. Speed and traffic disruptions

Road segment speeds in Fig. 6 reflect the effect of traffic streams at both
intersections under peak hour, as a saturation condition (a, b) and with a rela-
tively free traffic flow (c, d). Zooming in to the east entry lanes, data collection
points are placed at 100 m from the nodes. Among those, a complete saturation
365 occurs in the roundabout intersection around the simulation minute 22, where
the average operating speed of vehicles greatly declines, reaching eventually the
point where the density is determined by the length of the vehicles. The problem
of unbalanced intersections have been addressed in [55]; the high traffic stream
from certain input lanes is causing queues on other lanes, i.e. the ones coming
370 from the east. On the other hand, with a 25% flow reduction, the roundabout
intersection experiences higher average speeds than the signalised crossing.

Figure 6: Average vehicle speed (top): roundabout peak hour (a), signalised crossing peak hour (b), roundabout 25% traffic reduction (c), crossing 25% traffic reduction (d) for the 1st case. Data collection points measuring speed over the simulated hour (bottom).

Moreover, traffic disruptions such as travel delay and the number of stops can reflect the capacity of the road design. In this regard, the simulation hour is divided in four quarters. The 5 min buffer at the beginning and the end of the simulation hour are not included in the calculations. Average values of delay
 375 (s), number of stops per vehicle and travel time (15 min) are plotted in Fig. 7 for the two intersection types, with both the peak hour and the 25% traffic reduction.

The delay is computed for every vehicle that completes the travel time route.
 380 For that, an ideal travel time is calculated corresponding to the time that it will take for each vehicle to travel if other vehicles or signal controls were not present. For the peak hour, the average vehicles delay difference between the two intersection types becomes more evident as heavy vehicles are removed.

With the reduced configuration, the roundabout greatly improves its behaviour
 385 in terms of average delay time (50% reduction) and number of stops (65-75%
 reduction). Also, the average vehicle travel time greatly decreases (around 60-
 75% less travel time) for both intersection types. Roundabouts can be seen as
 an opportunity to reduce fuel consumption and improve air and noise quality
 through a diminution of acceleration cycles, as well as less idling time [17].

Figure 7: Average number of vehicle stops (left), average time delay of vehicles (centre) and average travel time of vehicles (right) for both intersection types, including peak hour and 25% traffic reduction. Averages made from information collected every 15 minutes of analysis.

390 These behaviours impact the output source power of each vehicle and hence,
 the resulting sound environment. The unbalanced situation of intersections can
 be observed in the speed distribution at the data collection points located on
 the entry lanes at the sidewalks, correspondingly named as E-W entry road and
 W-E entry road. In the first case (left), speed distributions are very similar for
 395 both intersection types (see Fig. 8), independently of traffic reduction, as the
 traffic flow is not congested. Contrary, for the west-east entry road (right), the
 congested situation at the roundabout is observed; the majority of the time the
 speed is less than 10 km/h and 70% of the time the vehicles are queuing more
 than 100 s. When reducing the traffic, the behaviour of this intersection type
 400 at the collection points is drastically changed, resembling the crossing intersec-
 tion type speed distribution. Traffic modelling parameters might have a large
 influence in these results and availability of local data regarding gap acceptance
 could refine the model as done in the study by [56]. It is remarkable that the
 researchers found a good agreement between the VISSIM traffic simulation re-
 405 sults and the observed field data as the follow-up headway variations found in
 the field data are reflected in the software.

Figure 8: Speed distribution at data collection points on the west entry lane (left) and the east entry lanes (right) for the 1st case under the two traffic configurations at both intersection types.

4.2. Effect of acceleration and deceleration

Vehicle interactions are increased at intersections, principally at congested ones. As traffic stream and interactions increment, the speed tends to decrease. The patterns of vehicle accelerations and decelerations are influenced by those interactions, having repercussions on the source strength. Fig. 9 shows the relation of speed (km/h) and source power (dBA) with acceleration (m/s^2), plotted as the amount of vehicle records. Due to the large number of records, a logarithmic scale is used to show the dynamics. As acceleration values increase, the sound power levels do as well, however, within the signalised crossing intersection the source strength is more spread, shifted towards higher sound power levels as acceleration increases.

Figure 9: Amount of records for speed (km/h) (left) and amount of records for sound power level (dBA) (right) at different acceleration values (m/s^2) for the first case (LV, MHV, HV) with a 25% traffic reduction from the peak hour. Colour grading ranges from blue as the lowest amount, to yellow, as the highest one.

The distribution of the sound power level for the simulation hour presents a distribution with Gaussian appearance for both intersection types, with a mean value of 91.4 dBA for the roundabout and 92.1 dBA for the signalised crossing, for the peak hour (Fig. 10). To see the effect of acceleration, it was tested to be removed when calculating the source strength, which resulted in very similar distributions (plot not included). The modelling assumption that deceleration leads to a reduction in sound power level, causes a partial cancelation effect between acceleration and deceleration, being highly relevant for the signalised crossing with its cycles.

Figure 10: Sound power level distribution including acceleration for the 1st case within the peak hour.

4.3. The effect of electric vehicles

To illustrate the effect that all-electric vehicles could have on the overall noise emission, sound power level distributions for both internal combustion engine vehicles (left) and all-electric ones (right) are shown in Fig. 11, for light vehicles (case 3). The results show that all-electric vehicles scenarios give a mean reduction of the output source strength of around 4.5 dBA.

Figure 11: Sound power level distribution over 0.1 s for internal combustion vehicles (right) and all-electric vehicles (left) at both intersection types within the peak hour. Light vehicles category composition.

4.4. Sound pressure levels at study points

To study the variations in the sound environment for different traffic configurations and the two intersection types, maps of equivalent sound pressure levels ($L_{Aeq,900s}$) are collected (see Fig. 12). Since traffic evolution is observed, results for different quarters of the hour are distinguished. The number of vehicles present at each quarter remains between 24-27% for both intersections. However, congestions and traffic composition at different vehicle routes ended in differences in the sound environment. As can be seen at the beginning of the roundabout simulation (a), a very similar sound pressure level is found at all lanes. In the second quarter (c), differences in the vehicles travel through the different routes are found compared to the first quarter. For example, in the roundabout scenario with 3 vehicle types composition, 23% more vehicles traveling from the south entry lanes, managed to reach their destinations during the second quarter, compared to the first quarter of hour. This is the result of an stochastic traffic behaviour and gap acceptance characteristics. On the other hand, compared to the first quarter of hour, 65% vehicles reached their destination from the entry east lanes during the second quarter of hour. In the crossing intersection type, the highest levels are concentrated at the node and at the south lanes for the first quarter of hour (b). However, for the second quarter of hour (d), a high traffic stream traveling from south to north is seen.

Figure 12: Sound pressure level (L_{Aeq}) at roundabout (left) and signalised crossing (right) for the peak hour in the 1st case for the 1st (a, b) and the 2nd quarter of the hour (c, d).

Concerning roundabouts, it has been stated that they have advantages in terms of road safety and capacity [17, 57]. The principal problem appears at unbalanced intersections [55], e.g. with a high traffic stream from one of the input lanes, causing queues on the upstream lanes, where vehicles have low chances to enter the roundabout. The previous conduct is recognisable in the equivalent sound pressure level difference as function of selected study points (see Fig. 13). For the peak hour (left), the points located close to the intersection (1-4) have a higher noise level for the signalised crossing, making it clear that the stop-and-go driving behaviour for these locations is having a large impact. When traffic is not congested, as in the west lanes, the study points located further away from the sources (5 and 8) hold a lower level for the roundabout intersection type. In the study points placed at the sidewalks of west lanes (9 and 12), the noise level is about the same for both intersection types, responding to a low traffic stream (<150 veh/h) in comparison with the rest of the layout. However, in the study points next to the east lanes (10 and 11), the roundabout intersection ends up with around 3 dB more (L_{Aeq}) than the signalised crossing. This responds to the unbalanced intersection situation, where the traffic stream

470 from east lanes is hindered by the high traffic flow from south entry lanes, i.e. the instantaneous demand exceeds the instantaneous capacity of the intersection, losing its efficiency. Vehicles are queuing for long periods of time, forcing constant stops on the whole lane, making the intersection more similar to a highly congested crossing.

475 As traffic is reduced by 25% (right), the variations are smeared out for the majority of the study points, except for the ones located at the node, where the crossing type is between 2 and 5 dB (L_{Aeq}) noisier than the roundabout. These results are aligned with previous studies on noise impact comparison between transport intersection types with stable flows. The studies showed that when

480 traffic dynamics is accounted, around 2.5 dB (L_{Aeq}) reduction could be gained from a roundabout intersection compared to a signalised one. However, since noise emission is extremely sensitive to the level of service, this is only achieved when light and medium traffic situations are represented [9, 58, 59].

Figure 13: Difference in sound pressure level at the selected study points. Peak hour (left) and 25% traffic reduction (right).

485 When using common noise mapping techniques, the reduction in L_{Aeq} is expected to be about 1.25 dB when the traffic is decreased by 25%. Similar reductions are found for the light vehicles case, with an average reduction among all study points of 1.24 dB (SD=0.32) for the crossing and 1.3 dB (SD=0.13) for the roundabout (see Fig. 14).

Figure 14: Difference in sound pressure level at the selected study points between the peak hour flow and 25% traffic reduction for the roundabout (left) and the crossing (right) intersection types.

However, an extra bonus in terms of reduction using the proposed method-
 490 ology, showing higher reduction values when all vehicle types are present, especially at situations that go from string congestions to a good flow (points 10-11), as in the roundabout case. Here, the average reduction among all selected study points reached 2.7 dB (SD=1.1) with a maximum reduction of 5 dB (L_{Aeq}). For the signalised crossing, the average reduction reached 1.8 dB (SD=0.66).

495 4.5. Contribution maps and time patterns

As previously mentioned, time patterns bring a number of excellent opportunities to study the sound in the built environment. Fig. 15 illustrates these differences, where higher dynamics are present at the crossing intersection type.

Figure 15: $L_{Aeq,1s}$ (dBA) at study point 2 for roundabout and signalised crossing intersection. 1st (top), 2nd (centre) and 3rd (bottom) cases.

500 In terms of sound pressure level, roads may be contributing differently to a certain study point, depending on vehicle type, road layout, speed limit, etc.

Although the largest contribution may come from a particular road far away, the maximum sound pressure level may come from somewhere else. In this sense, these road contributors may be susceptible to changes in e.g. crossings
 505 yield, speed reductions, location of buildings and street furniture elements, etc. To study this aspects, roads are here grouped into segments, gathering lanes of same direction, for each of the four roads. The equivalent sound pressure level ($L_{Aeq,900s}$), as well as the peak sound pressure level (L_{peak}) segment contribution to a certain point are shown for the light vehicle configuration roundabout (see
 510 Fig. 16). The contribution of the peak sound pressure level is greater in the east entrance lanes, helping to locate possible problems, whereas the equivalent sound pressure level contribution map points to both the south and the east lanes as responsables for the high levels at the receiver. The peak level contribution could be a better indicator than the equivalent level for e.g. sleep disturbance,
 515 highlighting problematic situations, however, such an indicator contains large uncertainties, whereas an indicator like L_{10} could have a more stable or constant behaviour (shown below). The suggested tool is proposed as a demonstrator of the possibilities that the analysis based on time-pattern could give.

Figure 16: $L_{Aeq,900s}$ (top) and $L_{peak,900s}$ (bottom) contribution to study point 2 per segment during the second quarter of simulation. Roundabout including only light vehicles.

4.6. Statistical indicators, calm periods and events

520 This section summarises two examples of results in terms of statistical indicators, calm periods and noise events. The interest is to find explanations on the differences between the intersection types and their receiver points regarding mean-energy-based descriptors and time-pattern-based indicators. Fig. 17

includes the analysis of study point 1 (top) located close to the nodes, and 10
 525 (bottom), at the sidewalk of the east exit lanes. The situations are compared
 among the two intersection types and the three study cases. The time-pattern-
 based descriptor Centre of Mass Time (CMT), illustrates the opportunities to
 recover from noisy periods. The inclusion of heavy vehicles gave place to larger
 CMT (L_{50}) clusterings, with very similar numbers at both intersection types.
 530 The number of events may help to characterise the rhythm of variations in sound
 level [60]. The number of events exceeding L_{10} and L_{50} display differences when
 the traffic configuration changes for both study points. Overall, the crossing
 intersection type shows the higher values of NE L_{10} (between 20 and 65% more
 events). For the NE L_{50} , the same phenomenon occurs. A negative correlation
 535 between the L_{10} and the NE L_{10} is found with vehicle type configurations,
 where the L_{10} generally decreases as heavy vehicles are removed, meaning that
 the reduction in the L_{10} threshold results generally in a higher number of events
 exceeding L_{10} . This behaviour may reflect a better sound environment; for ex-
 ample, very low values of foreground sound level would mean a higher number
 540 of events exceeding L_{10} . In this sense, next to the sidewalk (study point 10),
 the number of events above the foreground sound level (NE L_{10}) is tremen-
 dously increased as heavy vehicles are removed from both intersection types,
 around 3.5 times more events in the roundabout and two times in the signalised
 intersection type.

Figure 17: Statistical indicators, calm periods and events at the roundabout (left) and the signalised crossing (right) intersection types, for study points 1 and 10.

545 L_{10} has been used to present road traffic noise exposures as a measurement
of the noise that is intruding. However, it has been argued that these statisti-
cal descriptors do not reflect the sound fluctuations [60]. Using the number of
events exceeding L_{10} , as well as the novel indicator Centre of Mass Time below
 L_{10} (CMT L_{10}) may help to understand the intersection behaviours at certain
550 receivers when traffic volumes and engine characteristics vary. Differences be-
tween the node vicinity (study points 1-4) and the sidewalks (study points 9-12)
are reflected in Figure 18 with light vehicles included.

When combustion engine vehicles are studied, the highest values of L_{10} (left) are
found at the node vicinity of the signalised crossing. The traffic stream reduc-
555 tion has almost no impact on the L_{A10} values, however, the number of events
exceeding L_{A10} is affected. In this sense, it would be expected that as L_{A10}
values decrease, a higher number of noisy periods would occur, responding to
the lower values of peak sound level. The previous happens for the roundabout
scenario, however, at the signalised crossing certain study points increase their
560 noisy events number. Higher reductions in L_{A10} values and number of noisy
events are present when combustion engine vehicles on the peak hour simula-
tion are substitute by all-electric ones at both intersection types. Also, higher
clusters of periods of time (CMT) below L_{A10} , denoted CMT L_{10} (right), are
found when traffic stream is reduced or vehicles are substituted by all-electric
565 ones. This effect takes place principally at the signalised intersection.

Figure 18: L_{10} , number of events above L_{10} and centre of mass of time lengths below L_{10} at selected study points for both intersection types within the third case (only LV). Peak hour, 25% traffic reduction and only electric vehicles scenarios.

To study the time exposure, the time ratio (TR) within certain noise levels showed differences between internal combustion engine vehicles and electric ones

(Fig. 19). As an example, for the roundabout, more than 80% of the time at points 9-12 are submitted to L_{Aeq} values between 60 and 70 dB. When vehicles are replaced by electric ones, this number is reduced to about 40%. Next to the node (1-4), the noise exposure is reduced with the introduction of electric vehicles, however, during the vast majority of the time, the exposure is still above 60 dBA (64-82%).

Figure 19: Time ratio (TR) for all study points under certain equivalent noise level for the roundabout intersection type with internal combustion engine vehicles (left) and all-electric vehicles (right).

4.7. Difference maps on statistical descriptors and noise events

As an intuitive illustrated version of noise descriptors to help in the early decisions of an urban development, the following results show a series of difference maps for the two intersection types in question (see Figs. 20, 21). The differences are represented by the colour, where yellow means a higher value for the roundabout scenario and blue for the crossing one.

Fig. 20 shows the differences in terms of source strength output, where all entry or exit lanes are integrated into one. In this way, the total differences are reflected, regardless of the road configuration characteristics, e.g. number of lanes, turning lanes, etc. The results show that the stop-and-go behaviour generally has a large effect on the sound power level. For case 3 (LV), the high congestion on the roundabout scenario is giving the same sound power level as the crossing one for the east entry lanes, resulting in a very small difference there. The exit lanes of the roundabout have a higher integrated source strength, since vehicles leaving the roundabout are intended to reach their desired speed, requiring the vehicles to accelerate there.

Figure 20: Integration of lanes at each direction: sound power level (dBA) difference (Roundabout - Crossing) for case 1(left), case 2 (centre), case 3 (right).

590 Fig. 21 shows a series of peak hour difference maps of the total area of study, for the three traffic configurations, 1st (left), 2nd (centre) and 3rd (right) columns. These maps are showing the differences in the urban layout, which means that they are not integrated into one lane as the previous figure. The possibilities of the difference maps can be expanded to the study of other acoustic indicators. The occurrence of noise events is often related to a high variance in level [11]. For that reason, the temporal distribution is represented by maps both of L_{A10} (peak) and L_{A90} (background). In the study of L_{A10} (a,b,c), the differences disappeared almost completely when only light vehicles are present, with differences around 2 dBA, as reflected in the selected study points in Fig. 18

595 (left). Regarding the background noise level (d,e,f), represented as L_{A90} , the crossing is, in general, louder than in the roundabout (maximum differences around 6 dBA). To assess the temporal dynamics in a unique map, the indicator $L_{10} - L_{90}$ is shown in (g,h,i). The variation is similar for both intersection types for the large majority of the area, nevertheless, $L_{10} - L_{90}$ is higher at the

600 (left). Regarding the background noise level (d,e,f), represented as L_{A90} , the crossing is, in general, louder than in the roundabout (maximum differences around 6 dBA). To assess the temporal dynamics in a unique map, the indicator $L_{10} - L_{90}$ is shown in (g,h,i). The variation is similar for both intersection types for the large majority of the area, nevertheless, $L_{10} - L_{90}$ is higher at the

605 east side for the roundabout scenario (maximum difference is 10 dB). For case 3, differences at the vicinity of the noise sources are appearing more strongly. This type of analysis can be useful not only to improve the traffic layout and the outdoor sound environment, but moreover, in the establishment of building uses.

Figure 21: Difference maps. Roundabout relative to crossing for case 1(left), case 2 (centre), case 3 (right).

610 5. Discussion

The present paper aims to study transport management and traffic design in the built environment and the consequences for the sound environment from a micro-scale perspective. For this purpose, a tool capable of studying time variations is developed, combining microscopic traffic simulations and noise calculations including both emission and exposure. The tool intends to bring further knowledge to the current urban planning practice through an anticipatory design that includes the study of the sound environment under real situations based on time-pattern variations.

The tool incorporates the influence of vehicle kinematics in a way to obtain records of individual vehicles of different types, in terms of location, acceleration and velocity, as function of time. The output is used as input for a series

of in-house developed Matlab scripts to estimate at first, the output source strength of each vehicle as function of time. Second, the exposure analysis for different traffic configurations and vehicle categories is made through the study
625 of dynamic maps, contribution maps, statistical indicators and time-pattern analysis, including e.g. calm periods and events. Future incorporation of air attenuation will make the tool reliable to further distances. Also, more data on the variability of the output power level would be useful to update the model to current and future scenarios. The results presented are limited to the selected
630 intersection configurations, including a roundabout and a signalised crossing. However, the developed tool can be applied to different dynamic traffic simulations. In this regard, some of the conclusions are valid as well for other situations.

The tool presents multiple possibilities to study the sound environment. Especially, contribution maps based on time patterns are an opportunity to locate
635 possible conflicts towards a certain point of interest. There, both equivalent and peak sound pressure level maps are included as a powerful graphic tool. The inclusion of contribution maps apart from these, may bring opportunities to study certain indicators of interest related to nuisance (e.g. L_5 , L_1 or L_{peak}).
640 Moreover, the inclusion of mean-energy-based descriptors as well as time-pattern-based indicators provides several options to study not only nuisance, but, moreover, human activities interference. To represent the dynamics of the traffic noise signal, the study includes the clustering of quiet periods through the novel indicator Centre of Mass Time lengths below a certain value (CMT) and through
645 the number of events above a certain threshold at different locations. This may bring up opportunities to use a certain indicator of interest to take actions at selected locations according to the specific space functions and human activities developed in such space.

When there are heavy vehicles at roundabouts, the implicit rule of yielding to
650 vehicles within it results in higher congestions in certain traffic links. This type of vehicle needs a bigger gap to enter the roundabout, turning it into a complex intersection. In order to improve the resulting sound environment, the incor-

poration of metering signals for the roundabout [55, 56] improve the efficiency of unbalanced roundabouts to a large extent. On the other hand, the future inclusion of self-driving vehicles, would make the roundabouts more efficient i.e. the workload is placed on the driver instead of on the driver. The vehicle would then have the ability to adjust its speed to allow another vehicle to enter or exit the intersection. However, this new technology may be subjected to further study as it could better respond to different traffic configurations and road designs (e.g. location of pedestrian crossings).

The tool presented in this paper is under continual development. Future work will look toward the improvement of input data (e.g. acceleration and deceleration profiles), as well as the inclusion of pedestrian crossings. Also, the implementation of a more advanced propagation model, including air attenuation and the effect of buildings, is planned to be included, to improve the closeness to real situations in the built environment.

This type of analysis may help in the development of public space and the appropriateness of the sound environment to both activities and functions developed. In this sense, it has been argued that auralisation techniques may provide a very powerful tool for communication with city stakeholders. The presented tool, based on time-pattern analysis, can be of great use in feeding road traffic data to auralisation models. Moreover, the study of future urban traffic scenarios could also provide information to the study and development of kinetic buildings, i.e. dynamic structures with operable elements that have the capacity to adapt to changes, for example, in the outdoor sound environment.

One purpose of the paper is to enlighten the impact that traffic management decisions have on the built environment, by having a greater consideration for the sound environment at the beginning of the urban planning processes [61].

The overall concept of the tool presented here is to give input for bridging the gap between the urban planning practice and the current situation in cities.

6. Acknowledgments

This research was partially supported through the People Programme (Marie Curie Actions) of the EU's 7th Framework Programme FP7/2007-2013 under REA grant agreement n290110, SONORUS Urban Sound Planner. We thank
 685 our colleagues in the project who provided insight and expertise that greatly assisted the research.

This research has made use of the software VISSIM provided by PTV Group. The authors would like to thank the anonymous referees for helping to improve this article.

690 References

- [1] C. Nugent, N. Blanes, J. Fons, M. Sáinz de la Maza, M. Ramos, F. Domingues, et. al., Noise in Europe 2014, EEA Report 10/2014, European Environment Agency (2014).
- [2] Night noise guidelines for Europe, Tech. rep., World Health Organisation (WHO), Copenhagen, Denmark (2009).
 695
- [3] European Environment Agency, Exposure to and annoyance by traffic noise. TERM 05, Tech. rep., EEA (2014).
- [4] European Union, European Union Directive 2002/49/EC relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise, in: Official Journal of the European Communities, no. L189, 2002.
 700
- [5] M. Nilsson, R. Klæboe, J. Bengtsson, J. Forssén, M. Hornikx, B. Van der Aa, ... J. Young Hong, Novel solutions for Quieter and Greener Cities. HOSANNA workshop summary brochure (2013).
- [6] J. Forssén, W. Kropp, T. Kihlman, Introduction to traffic noise abatement, in: M. Nilsson, J. Bengtsson, R. Klæboe (Eds.), Environmental Methods for Transport Noise Reduction, CRC Press, Florida, 2014, Ch. Introduction to traffic noise abatement.
 705

- [7] T. Kihlman, W. Kropp, W. Lang, Quieter cities of the future, Tech. rep., Chalmers University of Technology (2014).
- 710 [8] C. Steele, A critical review of some traffic noise prediction models, *Applied Acoustics* 62 (2001) 271–287.
- [9] E. Chevallier, A. Can, M. Nadji, L. Leclercq, Improving noise assessment at intersections by modelling traffic dynamics, *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 14 (2009) 100–110.
- 715 [10] A. Can, L. Leclercq, Selecting noise source and traffic representations to capture road traffic noise dynamics near traffic signals, *Acta Acustica United Ac* 95 (2009) 259–269.
- [11] L. Brown, Issues in the measurement of sleep-related noise events in road traffic streams, in: *Proc. of Acoustics 2013, Conference of the Australian Acoustical Society*, Victor Harbor, Australia, 2013, pp. 1–5.
- 720 [12] F. Rudzik, L. Thiesse, R. Pieren, J. Wunderli, M. Brink, N. Probst-Hensch, et. al, Effects of continuous and intermittent transportation noise on sleep fragmentation, in: *Proc. of the 45th International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering, Inter-noise 2016*, 2016, pp. 7726–7732.
- 725 [13] M. Björkman, Community noise annoyance: Importance of noise levels and the number of noise events, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 151 (3) (1991) 497–503.
- [14] M. Maurin, Some algebra and statistics on isolated noise events, in: *Proc. of Acoustics 2008, Paris*, 2008, pp. 214–251.
- 730 [15] T. Sato, T. Yano, M. Björkman, R. Rylander, Road traffic noise annoyance in relation to average noise level, number of events and maximum noise level, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 223 (5) (1999) 775–784.
- [16] A. Can, L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, J. Defrance, Accounting for traffic dynamics improves noise assessment: Experimental evidence, *Applied Acoustics* 70 (6) (2009) 821–829.
- 735

- [17] L. Rodegerdts, J. Bansen, C. Tiesler, J. Knudsen, E. Myers, M. Johnson, et. al., NCHRP Report 672: Roundabouts: An Informational Guide, 2nd ed., Tech. rep., Transportation Research Board of the National Academies, Washington, D. C. (2010).
- 740 [18] M. Trueblood, J. Dale, Simulating roundabouts with vissim, in: The 2nd Urban Street Symposium, Anaheim, California, 2003.
- [19] B. De Coensel, T. De Muer, I. Yperman, D. Botteldooren, The influence of traffic flow dynamics on urban soundscapes, *Applied Acoustics* 66 (2) (2005) 175–194.
- 745 [20] A. Can, L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, J. Defrance, Capturing urban traffic noise dynamics through relevant descriptors, *Applied Acoustics* 69 (12) (2008) 1270–1280.
- [21] A. Can, E. Chevallier, M. Nadji, L. Leclercq, Dynamic traffic modeling for noise impact assessment of traffic strategies, *Acta Acust united Ac* 96 (3)
750 (2010) 482–493.
- [22] B. De Coensel, A. Can, B. Degraeuwe, I. De Vliege, D. Botteldooren, Effects of traffic signal coordination on noise and air pollutant emissions, *Environmental Modelling and Software* 35 (2012) 74–83.
- [23] A. Bhaskar, E. Chung, M. Kuwahara, Development and implementation
755 of the areawide Dynamic ROad traffic NoisE (DRONE) simulator, *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 12 (5) (2007) 371–378.
- [24] L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, Dynamic evaluation of urban traffic noise, in: *Proc. of the 17th International Congress on Acoustics*. Rome, 2001.
- 760 [25] A. Can, L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, Dynamic estimation of urban traffic noise: influence of traffic and noise source representations, *Applied Acoustics* 69 (2008) 858–867.

- [26] J. Hamet, F. Bernard, S. Doisy, J. Lelong, E. le Duc, New vehicle noise emission for French traffic noise prediction, *Applied Acoustics* 71 (2010) 861–869.
- 765
- [27] S. Kephelopoulos, M. Paviotti, F. Anfosso-Lédée, Reference report on Common Noise Assessment Methods in EU (CNOSSOS-EU), Tech. Rep. EUR 25379 EN, Publications Office of the EU, Luxembourg (2012).
- [28] A. Can, L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, Dynamic urban traffic noise: Do individualized emission laws improve estimation?, in: *Proc. of International Congress on Acoustics*. Madrid, 2007.
- 770
- [29] A. Can, L. Leclercq, J. Lelong, D. Botteldooren, Traffic noise spectrum analysis: dynamic modeling vs. experimental observations, *Applied Acoustics* 71 (2010) 764–770.
- [30] A. Brown, An overview of concepts and past findings on noise events and human response to surface transport noise, in: *Proc. of the 43rd International Congress on Noise Control Engineering Inter-noise 2014*, 2014.
- 775
- [31] B. De Coensel, A. Brown, D. Botteldooren, Modeling road traffic noise using distributions for vehicle sound power level, in: *Proc. of the 41st International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering Inter-Noise 2012*, 2012.
- 780
- [32] J. Defrance, J. Palacino, M. Baulac, Acoustic auscultation of urban bike-ways, in: *Proc. of the CFA 2010*, Lyon, 2010.
- [33] R. Wiedemann, U. Reiter, Microscopic traffic simulation: the simulation system mission, background and actual state., Tech. rep., CEC project ICARUS (V1052) final report, vol 2, Appendix A (1992).
- 785
- [34] M. Fellendorf, P. Vortisch, *Fundamentals of traffic simulation*, Springer, 2010, Ch. Microscopic Traffic Flow Simulator VISSIM.

- 790 [35] V. Gallelli, R. Vaiana, Roundabout intersections: evaluation of geometric and behavioural features with vissim, in: Proc. of TRB National Roundabout Conference, Kansas City, Missouri, USA, 2008.
- [36] Z. Li, M. DeAmico, M. Chitturi, A. Bill, D. Noyce, Calibration of vissim roundabout model: A critical gap and follow-up headway approach, in: Transportation Research Board 92nd Annual Meeting (No. 13-1176), 795 Wahington, D.C., 2013.
- [37] F. Mannering, S. Wahsburn, Principles of Highway Engineering and Traffic Analysis. 5th Ed., Wiley, New York, 2013.
- [38] PTV VISSIM, Vissim 6 user manual, in: PTV AG, 2013.
- [39] M. Pallas, M. Bérengier, R. Chatagnon, M. Czuka, M. Conter, M. Muirhead, 800 Towards a model for electric vehicle noise emission in the European prediction method CNOSSOS-EU, Applied Acoustics 113 (2016) 89–101.
- [40] M. Pallas, J. Kennedy, I. Walker, R. Chatagnon, M. Bérengier, J. Lelong, FOREVER Noise emission of electric and hybrid electric vehicles, Tech. Rep. Deliverable FOREVER WP2 D2-1 v4, CEDR (2015).
- 805 [41] R. Nota, R. Barelds, D. van Maercke D, Technical Report Harmonoise WP3 Engineering method for road traffic and railway noise after validation and fine-tuning. Deliverable of WP3 of the Harmonoise project, Technical Report HAR32TR-040922-DGMR20 (2005).
- [42] H. L. Nielsen, Road traffic Noise. Nordic prediction method. TemaNord 810 1996:525, Tech. rep., Nordic Council of Ministers (1996).
- [43] U. Sandberg, Noise emissions of road vehicles effect of regulations: Final report 01-1, Noise News International 9 (3) (2001) 147–203.
- [44] J. Forssén, M. Hornikx, Statistics of a-weighted road traffic noise levels in shielded urban areas, Acta Acust united Ac 92 (2006) 998–1008.

- 815 [45] B. De Coensel, L. Brown, D. M. Tomerini, A road traffic noise pattern simulation model that includes distributions of vehicle sound power levels, *Applied Acoustics* 111 (2016) 170–178.
- [46] L. Brown, D. M. Tomerini, Distribution of the noise level maxima from the pass-by of vehicles in urban road traffic streams, *Road and Transport*
820 *Research* 20 (3) (2011) 41–54.
- [47] T. Gjestland, Research on community response to noise - in the last five years, in: *Proc. of the 9th Congress of the International Commission on the Biological Effects of Noise (ICBEN)*, Mashantucket, Connecticut, USA, 2008, pp. 556–561.
- 825 [48] J. Lambert, P. Champelovier, I. Vernet, Annoyance from high speed train noise: a social survey, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 15 (193) (1996) 21–28.
- [49] F. Hall, S. Taylor, S. Birnie, Activity interference and noise annoyance, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 103 (1985) 237–252.
- [50] Göteborg Stad, Älvstaden. Frihamnen district.
830 URL <http://alvstaden.goteborg.se/vara-delomraden/frihamnen/>
- [51] Trafikverket, Utformning av vägar och gator [Design of roads and streets].
URL <http://www.trafikverket.se/for-dig-i-branschen/vag/Utformning-av-vagar-och-gator/>
- [52] National Research Council (U.S), HCM 2010 - Highway capacity manual,
835 Transportation Research Board, Washington, D.C. (2010).
- [53] Göteborg Stad. Trafik-kontoret, Trafikmängder på olika gator [Traffic volumes at different streets].
- [54] B. De Coensel, D. Botteldooren, Traffic signal coordination: a measure to reduce the environmental impact of urban road traffic?, in: *Proc. of the*
840 *40th Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (Inter-noise)*, Osaka, Japan, 2011.

- [55] M. Martin-Gasulla, A. García, A. Moreno, Benefits of Metering Signals at Roundabouts with Unbalanced Flow - Patterns in Spain, *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board* 2585 (2016) 20–28. 845
- [56] M. Martin-Gasulla, A. García, A. Moreno, C. Llorca, Capacity and operational improvements of metering roundabouts in Spain, *Transportation Research Procedia* 15 (2016) 295–307.
- [57] A. Vadeby, U. Brüde, Korsningsutformning: en kunskapsöversikt [Junction design - a review], *VTI Rapport 554*, Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute (VTI) (2006). 850
- [58] M. Berengier, Acoustical impact of traffic flowing equipments in urban areas, in: *Proc. of Forum Acusticum Seville*, 2002.
- [59] B. De Coensel, F. Vanhove, S. Logghe, D. Botteldooren, Noise emission corrections at intersections based on microscopic traffic simulation, in: *Proc. of European Conference on Noise Control*. Tampere., 2006. 855
- [60] A. Can, P. Aumond, S. Michel, B. De Coensel, C. Ribeiro, D. Botteldooren, C. Lavandier, Comparison of noise indicators in an urban context, in: *Proc. of the 45th International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (Inter-Noise 2016)*., 2016. 860
- [61] W. Kropp, J. Forssén, L. Estévez-Mauriz (Eds.), *Urban Sound Planning – the SONORUS project*, Chalmers University of Technology, 2016.